

Bibliometric Analysis of Managerial Skills and Performance of Small to Medium Enterprises (SMEs)

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ABSTRACT: In the era of globalization, small and medium enterprises (SMEs) have a very important role in the economy of a country, including Indonesia. One of the factors that may influence the performance of SMEs is the managerial skills and skills possessed by the owners and managers of SMEs. Good managerial skills can help SMEs manage existing resources more effectively and efficiently, which can improve their performance. However, in the context of product SMEs in wetlands, there is still limited information regarding the influence of managerial skills on the performance of SMEs.

KEYWORDS: Managerial Skills, Performance, SMEs

I. INTRODUCTION

In the era of globalization moment, SMEs have a very important role in the economy of a country (Misra & Kumar, 2017), including Indonesia. One of the possible factors influencing SME performance is Skills and managerial skills owned by SME owners and managers (Smith & Brown, 2018). Skills good managerial can help SMEs manage the source power they have more effectively and efficiently, which can increase the performance of these SMEs (Smith & Brown, 2020). However, in the product SME context land wet, still there are limitations in information related influence of Skills managerial on the performance of these SMEs.

1. Introduction

Based background behind the formulation problem in the study This is:

- How is the article Skills Managerial and Product SME Performance Land classified wet?
- How do trend research Skills managerial in SMEs?
- What topic Skills do managerial SMEs that provide opportunities For study more carry on?

2. Research Objectives

Objectives of the study This is:

- To analyze in a way bibliometrics Skills managerial and product SME performance land wet 2019-2024 with gather articles from journal indexed Scopus.
- For answer trend research Skills managerial in SMEs
- To explain the topic Skills managerial SMEs that provide opportunity For study more carry on.

3. Benefits of Research

Research This expectation can give a significant contribution to the development literature about the influence of Skills managerial on the performance of SMEs, especially product

SMEs land wet. Research results This expectation can become a reference for SME owners and managers in increasing Skills managerial To increase SME performance. Additionally, research is also expected can give useful information for governments and institutions related to designing policies that can support SME product development land.

II. LITERATURE

Review 1. Definition Skills Managerial

Skills managerial is the ability individual to manage source power and lead a team To reach an objective organization. According to Robbins & Coulter (2017), skills managerial consist of three aspect main, i.e. Skills technical, skills humanity, and skills conceptual. Skills This is very important for a manager in managing business small and medium-sized (SME) sector product land wet.

2. Understanding SME

Performance of Wetland Products SME Product Performance land can be measured from various aspects, like productivity, profitability, market share, and innovation products. According to Kuncoro, (2010), product SME performance land wet influenced by internal and external factors, including Skills management owned by the owner or the SME manager.

3. Relationship Between Skills Managerial and Performance of SME

Research previously has shown a connection positive between Skills managerial and SME performance. For example, research by Suharnomo (2015) finds that SME owners who own Skills Good managerial tend own perform more effort Good compared to those who don't own Skills the.

Therefore that's important for the owner or SME product manager to land wet To keep going develop Skills managerial.

4. Previous Studies Related Bibliometric

Analysis Bibliometric studies constitute method analysis used To identify trend research and influence Skills managerial to product SME performance land wet. Previous bibliometric research by Nurmalina. et.al.(2018) show that there is an enhanced interest in researchers in the study of the connection between Skills managerial and SME performance. Thus, bibliometric analysis can give deep insight into development study-related topics. Related Bibliometric Analysis with MSMEs too conducted by Bahit et al. (2022) which shows the need for a viable strategy developed To help MSMEs manage report business and finance with the use Simple and easy ERP (Enterprise Resource Planning) system.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

3.1. Defining Keywords

Search literature conducted in June 2024, using Publish or Perish (PoP) software with the keywords " Managerial skills", Small Medium Size Enterprises Performance" and "Performance of Wet land Products". Entire analyzed articles originate from the Scopus database with a range time 2019 to August 2024. Search the set provision analyzed articles originate from journals. So articles from ebooks, proceedings, letters news, and magazines No analyzed.

3.2. Initial Search Results

Search beginning with Publish or Perish (PoP) software with the words "Managerial skills", as many as 95 articles, "Small Medium Size Enterprises Performance" as many as 200 articles, and "Performance of Wet land Products" as many as 4 articles from journal indexed Scopus. Then, selected entirely published articles in Language UK, and we do too eliminated articles that weren't relevant with the keyword, which is not identified / Unidentified, and as many as 233 articles, so the journal remaining a total of 66 articles.

Table 1. shows a comparison of metric data from search beginning.

Filtering Initial Search	Number of Articles
Not any ability relevant managerial with SME performance	233
Criteria filtering search beginning	66
Total	299

3.3. Search Results Improvements

From the 299 results search initially, only 66 articles originated from appropriate journal criteria, then articles the

reselected based on ranking journals using the Schimagojr website. Only journals published in Q1 to Q4 journals will be analyzed using VOSviewer. Of the 299 articles, there are 233 articles No indexed Scopus, 66 articles occupied Q1 ranking. Table 2 shows the results improvement criteria filtering search.

Table 2. Refinements Details of Search Criteria

Improvement Search	Screening Number of Articles
Not listed from the Scimago list	26
Q1	40
Q2-Q3	0
Total	66

Then 66 articles were checked title, abstract, and author For compared to with article search beginning. So only 40 articles were submitted for criteria screening and a total of 26 articles No There is in the latest Scimago list in 2024 using the website <https://www.scimagojr.com/>.

3.4. Compiling Initial Data Statistics

Resulting in search after repair downloaded saved in device Mendeley software. All information important related papers, incl title, name author, abstract, keywords, and specifications journal (publication journal, year issues, volumes, issues, and pages) are exported to RIS format for analysis so that the article can classified based on year (Figure 1 Publication trends from year to year), rank journal (Figure 2. Number of Journal Citations whose articles are analyzed), country of origin publication (Table 4. Country of place article analyzed) and sources publications (Table 5. Source publication journal).

Figure 1. Publication Trends from year to year

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Publication related with keywords own amount highest in 2019, namely as many as 12 articles, and point lowest in 2023 of 1 article, 2024 not yet found article related with relevant keywords with study This.

Figure 2. Number of Journal Citations whose articles were analyzed

In Figure 2 you can see the highest number of citations occurred in 2020 and the lowest in 2023.

Table 4. Countries whose articles analyzed

Country	Number of Articles
United States	2
United Kingdom	2
Taiwan	1
Australia	1
Malaysia	1
Greece	1
Canada	2
Saudi Arabia	1
Chile	1
Poland	1
Spain	1
China	2
United Arab Emirates	1
Vietnamese	1
France	1
Portugal	1
North Macedonia	1
Qatar	1
South Korea	2
Pakistan	1
Cyprus	1
Nigeria	1
India	1
South Africa	1
Thailand	1
Iran	1
Austria	1
Slovakia	1
Indonesia	1
Zimbabwe	1

Italy	2
Turkey	1
Sweden	1
Ghana	1
Romania	1
Total	40

Figure 3. VOSviewer based on country of location study.

Based on Table 4 and Figure 3. 35 countries place study related with keywords in the study This means the study involves data collection or observation from 35 different countries. This matter shows that studying This nature internationally and encompassing various geographic areas, can give results broad. Data obtained from these various countries is Possibly used To understand patterns, trends, or phenomena certain things that apply globally or To compare differences and similarities between these countries.

University of Zilina	1
Sage Publications	1
POSTS	2
Korea Distribution Science Association (KODISA)	1
Taylor&Francis	1
Total	40

Table 5. Source Publication Journal

Publisher	Number of Articles
Elsevier	6
Wiley	6
MDPI	4
Palgrave Macmillan	1
Emerald Publishing	11
VGTU Press	1
Growing Science	2
Springer	1
Publisher Universiti Sains Malaysia	1
Cogent OA	1

2.5. Data analysis

This article serves bibliometric analysis for the terms "Performance", "Small Medium Enterprise" and "Managerial Skill" from the Scopus database. A bibliometric review of this paper using PoP software version 7.25.2877.7516 developed by Tarma Research Software Pty Ltd-Melbourne [9]. PoP Software launched in August 2020. Research This found 299 articles. Furthermore analyzed articles published in journals reputable with a Q1 ranking of 66 articles Then filtered Again with a check on schimago until 40 articles were obtained with Cites/Paper 23.04.

IV. RESEARCH RESULTS

4.1. Bibliometric Analysis of Skills Managerial and SME Performance

Analysis results from VOSviewer can be seen in Figure 4 below:

Figure 4. Topic Area Visualization Use VOSviewer use visualization network

Figure 4 shows A visualization word network or concept showing the connection between words or drafts in context certain. Following is an analysis of the picture:

a) Main Center:

- The word "performance" is at the center and has a lot of connections in other words, shows that This is the draft key in network This.
- The word "relationship" also has a significant connection, showing the importance of connection in context.

b) Clusters and Colors:

- Blue Cluster: Related to "performance", "research", "analysis", and "practice". This includes aspects of theoretical and practical performance.
- Red Cluster: Connected with "SMES performance", "adoption", "social", and "medium". It focuses on SME (Small and Medium Enterprises) performance and adoption of technology or practice social.
- Green Cluster: Includes "country", "managerial skills", "entrepreneur", and "innovation". This shows the connection between Skills managerial, entrepreneurial, and innovation in a country context.
- Purple Cluster: Linking "innovativeness", "medium-sized enterprise", and "firm performance". This shows a focus on the company's medium and innovation.

- Yellow Cluster: Includes "small", "network embeddedness", and "positive effect". This shows the importance of networks and their effects positive on the company.

c) Connection:

- There are many connections between the words indicating a connection complex between concepts.
- Words like "impact," "influence," "effect," and "practice" frequently appear as connection important, showing the interaction and impact of various factors on performance.

d) Draft Other Important:

- "Innovation", "entrepreneur", and "managerial skills" show the importance of innovation, entrepreneurship, and skills managerial in context performance.
- "Social", "economy", and "industry" indicate that context social, economic, and industrial are also important in analysis.

Overall, the picture describes a connection complex between various factors affecting performance, with a focus specifically on SMEs, innovation, entrepreneurship, and networks.

After taking into account frequent keyword frequency appears. Study this also maps the year For every keyword frequency (Figure 5. Visualization of topic areas use VOSviewer use overlay visualization). From the picture,

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You can see the frequency of frequent keywords appear and exist correlation with study that occurred in 2020 until in 2022.

Figure 5. Topic Area Visualization Use overlay visualization

Cluster-based color and time. Blue (2020), words like "adoption", "practical application", "SMEs performance", and "education" are colored blue. Show that study or topics This more Lots discussed in 2020. Green (2021), Words like "economy", "industry", "impact", and "influence" are in the color green. Show enhancement focus on aspects of the economy and industry as well as impact in 2021. Yellow (2022), words like "innovativeness," "medium-sized enterprise," and "network embeddedness" are colored yellow. Show that topics This more new and more often discussed in 2022.

Main Connection. Impact & Influence, words like "impact", "influence", and "effect" are highly connected, showing the importance of impact and influence in context performance. **Innovation & Adoption,** the words "innovation" and "adoption" frequently appear, indicating a connection between innovation and adoption technology/practice in increased performance.

Changes:

- **2020:** Focus on adoption, applications practical, and SME performance, p This shows that this year This is more focused on how SMEs adopt technology or practice new and its impact.
- **2021:** Focus shifted to an aspect of economy and industry, as well as its impact and influence, showing enhanced attention to context more economically wide.
- **2022:** Emphasis on innovation, company intermediate, and linkage network, shows more attention to the company intermediate and how innovation as well as network influence performance.

Apart from analyzing keyword frequency and frequency keyword year, research also analyzes frequency studies based on keywords between 2019 to 2024 (Figure 6). Topic area visualization uses VOSviewer use visualization density). The figure seen color the yellow thick, shows 40 articles from Q1 have been Lots researched about 'Performance'.

Figure 6. Topic Area Visualization uses visualization density.

V. RESEARCH CONCLUSION

This analyzed 40 articles published in Q1 journals based on data from Scimago with the themes "Managerial Skills", "Small Medium Size Enterprises Performance", and "Performance of Wetland Products". The following are several points main from the conclusion study:

1. Research Trends:

- An increased amount of research occurred in 2019, while in 2020 it experienced a decline, caused by the COVID-19 pandemic.
- Topic dominant research is SME performance and ERP (Enterprise Resource Planning), which shows an opportunity big for study more about ERP implementation in SMEs.

2. Visualization Topic Study:

- Bibliometric visualization shows a shift in focus study from 2020 to 2022, with emphasis mainly on keeping up with changing performance and relationships by topics new one has appeared every year.

3. Focus and Relationships Draft:

- The word "performance" is at the center network draft with Lots connection, which shows that This is a draft key.
- Connection strength is also seen in the words "relationship", "impact", "influence", and "effect", which show the interaction and impact of various factors on SME performance.
- Innovation, skills managerial, and entrepreneurial are also prominent as draft important in increasing SME performance.

4. Suggestions for Study Furthermore:

- The study furthermore recommended For focus on developing a model or framework that can help identify Skills the most influential managerial in increasing SME performance, especially in the sector product land wet.
- More case studies deep for understand the context of local areas and influencing factors implementation Skills managerial in practice Daily is also recommended.

REFERENCES

1. Bahit, M., Handayani, M., & Hayanto, R. (2022). Bibliometric Analysis of the Concept of Using Enterprise Resource Planning in the Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSME) Sector. *Advances in Economics, Busi*, 183 (3), 5–9. <https://doi.org/10.18421/TEM113-31>
2. Kuncoro, M. (2010). *Introduction to Microeconomics: An Analysis of Structure, Behavior, and Performance Approaches*. UPP STIM YKPN.
3. Misra, S. C., & Kumar, V. (2017). Impact of managerial skills on small business performance: A study of manufacturing and service sectors in India. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 66 (8), 1046–1069.
4. Nurmalina, R. (2018). Bibliometric Analysis of the Effect of Managerial Skills on the Performance of Wetland Product SMEs. *Journal of SME Management*, 3 (2), 45–60.

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5. Robbins, S. P., & Coulter, M. (2017). *Management*. Pearson.
6. Smith, J., & Brown, A. (2018). The impact of managerial skills on small business performance: A bibliometric analysis. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 56 (3), 345–362.
7. Smith, J., & Brown, A. (2020). The impact of managerial skills on small and medium enterprises performance: A bibliometric analysis. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 35 (2), 123–135.
8. Suharnomo. (2015). *Entrepreneurship: Theory, Practice, and Cases*. Andi Offset.